

ISSUES OF MEDIA EDUCATION IN THE MODERN INFORMATION SETTING

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ABSTRACT

This article highlights the importance of media and technology in teaching English of young people living in today's technological age. In addition, the reforms in media education and their positive results in education today are discussed. The purpose of the article is to provide information about how fast media education is growing and what great results have been achieved through it in education, and how important media education is in today's information environment. Various manuals, articles and dictionaries were taken as sources for the article.

Keywords: media, multimedia, information technology, media literacy

ZAMONAVIY AXBOROT MUHITIDA MEDIA TA'LIM MASALALARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqola bugungi texnologiya asrida yashayotgan yoshlarga xorijiy til o'rgatishda ya'ni ingliz tili o'qitishda media va texnologiyalarning ahamiyatini yoritib beradi. Undan tashqari, media ta'limida olib borilayotgan islohotlar va bugungi kunda ularning ta'limdagi ijobiy natijalari haqida fikr yuritiladi. Maqoladan ko'zlangan maqsad shuki, media ta'limining qanchalik tez o'sib borayotganligi va ta'limda u orqali qanday buyuk natijalarga erishilganligi hamda zamonaviy axborot muhitida media ta'limining qanchalik muhim ekanligi haqida ma'lumot berishdan iborat. Maqola uchun manba sifatida turli xil qo'llanmalar, maqolalar va lug'atlar olingan.

Kalit so'zlar: media, multimedia, axborot texnologiya, media savodxonligi

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ МЕДИАОБРАЗОВАНИЯ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ИНФОРМАЦИОННОЙ СРЕДЕ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье подчеркивается важность средств массовой информации и технологий в образовании молодых людей, живущих в современную

технологическую эпоху. Кроме того, обсуждаются реформы в медиаобразовании и их положительные результаты в современном образовании. Цель статьи – предоставить информацию о том, как быстро развивается медиаобразование и какие большие результаты благодаря ему достигнуты в образовании, а также насколько важно медиаобразование в современной информационной среде. В качестве источников для статьи были взяты различные пособия, статьи и словари.

Ключевые слова: СМИ, мультимедиа, информационные технологии, медиаграмотность

INTRODUCTION

Media literacy is an integral part of media education. At the same time, its appearances are increasing. Today, the concepts entering our language as a result of media analysis, i.e. media literacy, media education, media study, etc., are related to each other, but media information reception, sorting, analysis e tish, together with the concept of media literacy, the concepts of media education, media study, and media culture are used in the assessment. Improving the system of personnel training in the field of information technologies is one of the important conditions for the successful implementation of the "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy, the development of digital technologies and the wide implementation of them in the everyday life of the population. Measures taken to increase the efficiency of the system of vocational training and retraining in the field of information technologies create a solid foundation for providing state bodies and network organizations with qualified IT specialists. In particular, a school specialized in in-depth teaching of information and communication technologies named after Muhammad al-Khorazmi and branches of a number of foreign universities have been launched, and digital technology training centers are being gradually established in districts and cities. At the same time, the lack of qualified personnel in the labor market of the republic requires the improvement of educational programs and methods in the field of information technologies, and the strengthening of cooperation between educational institutions and IT companies.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Multimedia is a form of communication that uses a combination of different content forms such as writing audio, images, animations, or video into a single interactive presentation, in contrast to traditional mass media, such as printed material

or audio recordings, which features little to no interaction between users. Popular examples of multimedia include video podcasts, audio slideshows and animated videos.

Media - the plural of medium, broadly describes all channels of communication, including everything from printed paper to digital data. Media comprises news, art, educational content, and any form of information that can reach or influence people, including television, radio, books, magazines, and the internet.

Information technology (IT) is a set of related fields that encompass computer systems, software, programming languages and data and information processing and storage. IT forms part of information and communications technology. An information technology system (IT system) is generally an information system, a communications system, or, more specifically speaking, a computer system — including all hardware, software, and peripheral equipment — operated by a limited group of IT users, and an IT project usually refers to the commissioning and implementation of an IT system.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

At the moment, it is necessary to include the basics of media education in the curriculum of every educational institution, to explain its basics to students and young people in the educational process in schools in the form of interactive, various games, to choose what is necessary for the growing generation in the intense flow of information and allows him to be critically evaluated. Media is of great importance in teaching foreign languages. Today, teachers use many technological devices while teaching English to children. In addition, not only in school, but also in university, mass media is used effectively in teaching English. The media in the English Language development establishes a link between the human resources and the non-human resources. They are the different kinds of things which the teachers and the students use in the teaching learning process. Institutional resources help to enhance the teaching ability of English Language teachers. They help to bridge the communication gap between the teachers and learners by assisting the teachers to explain concepts better. They help English Language teachers to reduce the amount of talking and thus make their teaching more interesting and successful. They provide opportunity for learners to see, hear and handle and thus create a high degree of interest in English language. They offer a reality experience which stimulates self-activity on the part of learners. They make learning more concrete, crystallized, practical, applicable and meaningful. They

enhance the rate of retention of what students are taught. They change the role of the teacher as sole dispenser of knowledge to that of coordinator of learning experiences. They permit students to proceed at their own pace. They provide the learners with opportunities for practice. They stimulate thoughts and discussions of students. They inspire students to higher levels of achievement. This, in turn, serves as a basis for further strengthening of the citizenship position of young people in the future, to be able to objectively assess the events taking place in the world and make the right decisions.

Today, media literacy means knowing how and why information is being transmitted. Today's media, i.e. mass media, cinema, theater, types of art, cultural influences, any information transmitted through the Internet has a certain effect on a person and changes his worldview. The main purpose of the application of the above-mentioned concepts and the pursuit of media education, media literacy, media criticism and media studies today is the creation of information, understanding the process of its dissemination, commercial, political, economic, spiritual and to be able to evaluate the information that is being disseminated for cultural purposes. Media literacy is the study of media and is based on the following outcomes of media education and aims to:

- understanding the impact of media on individuals and society;
- understanding of mass communication process;
- ability to understand and analyze media texts;
- understanding the media context;
- creation of media texts and their analysis;
- the media sets the tasks of evaluating texts and sorting them

Media and information literacy is a set of knowledge, skills, attitudes, skills and practices that enable the effective acquisition, analysis, critical evaluation, interpretation, use, creation and distribution of information and media products using all necessary tools in creative activities. The multifold acceleration of the flow of information, the increase of positive information as well as negative information made it necessary to acquire media literacy. Traditionally, media literacy consisted of a person's ability to analyze literary texts and create quality texts.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be noted that today's importance of media and information technology, such as its application to education, is becoming an urgent issue. Today, we need to guide children, pupils and students in the correct and effective use of mass media. It is also desirable to improve the quality of education from such tools and for teachers to teach using them through their pedagogical skills.

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